
**RAINWATER HARVESTING SYSTEM FEASIBILITY STUDY FOR
MEDIUM-SCALE URBAN DEVELOPMENTS – THE BRABAZON
DEVELOPMENT CASE STUDY**

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Research dissertation submitted in fulfilment of the Master of Science in Environmental
Engineering

The University of Bath
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Date: 11 September 2020

Total Word Count: 15810

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Abstract

This research paper explores the feasibility of implementing a medium scale rainwater harvesting system using the first phase of the Brabazon Development as a case study. Using the Urban Water Optioneering Tool to simulate the complete urban water cycle for the 278 residential units, a quantified water balance is obtained and used as the feed information for the economic assessment. Built into the model simulation are variations to the occupancy (number of residents serviced), the consumption per person, the collection surface area and the runoff percentage. These variations generate a potential performance range. The best case scenario (maximised rainwater supply, minimised non-potable water demand) show a non-potable water demand of 9787m³/year and a total harvestable rainwater quantity of 13700m³/year. The worst case scenario (minimised rainwater supply and maximised non-potable water demand) shows a total non-potable water demand 39400m³/year and a total harvestable rainwater quantity of 7800m³/year. These best and worst case scenarios are then taken forward into the economic assessment which uses a net present value (NPV) approach to determine the return on investment period and the value of the investment after 30 years.

When limited to a capital expense of between £70 000 and £100 000, both the best and worst case performances show an economic benefit. The return on investment period varies between 11 and 29 years, and the NPV varying between £1 600 and £76 000. However, the system is infeasible in that the development owners, in this case YTL Developments, incur the entirety of the capital costs and potentially the operating and maintenance costs while the savings made from the reduced water bill benefits the homeowners. With the increasing threat that water scarcity and climate change have on urban areas, this rainwater harvesting system offers a suitable tool for adapting the Brabazon Development to limit the impact of uncertain future water resource availability. Additionally, the system shows an improved economic performance with an increasing water price and reduces the consumption of “over-treated” water by between 7800m³/year and 8700m³/year.

Table of Contents

Authorship.....	i
Abstract	ii
Table of Contents.....	iii
List of Figures.....	vi
List of Tables	vii
Chapter 1: Introduction.....	1
1.1 Background.....	1
1.1.1 Adapting Water Management Plans	2
1.1.2 The Role of Rainwater Harvesting	2
1.2 Project Details	3
1.2.1 The Brabazon Development.....	3
1.2.2 Project Aims & Objectives.....	5
1.2.3 Research Question	6
Chapter 2: Literature Review.....	7
2.1 Rainwater Harvesting Feasibility Case Studies	7
2.2 Simulation Software.....	9
2.2.1 Urban Water Optioneering Tool.....	10
Chapter 3: Research Methodology.....	13
3.1 Research Methodology Overview.....	13
3.2 Urban Water Cycle Simulations	14
3.2.1 Simulation Input Data.....	15
3.3 Economic Feasibility Assessments	17
3.3.1 Capital Expenses	18
3.3.2 Operating and Maintenance Expenses	19
3.3.3 Economic Benefit.....	19
Chapter 4: Urban Water Cycle Simulations.....	20

4.1	Urban Water Optioneering Tool	20
4.2	Supply Characteristics	21
4.2.1	Rainfall	21
4.2.2	Collection Surface Area	23
4.2.3	Rainwater Runoff	25
4.3	Demand Characteristics	25
4.3.1	Serviced Population.....	25
4.3.2	Water Performance Rating.....	27
4.4	Storage Facilities	29
4.4.1	Storage Capacity	29
4.4.2	Storage Tank Type	30
4.4.3	Treatment Requirements.....	31
4.5	Simulation Results	31
Chapter 5:	Economic Assessment	33
5.1	Return On Investment Calculation.....	33
5.1.1	Capital, Maintenance & Operating Expenses	34
5.1.2	System Savings	36
5.2	Economic Assessment Results.....	37
Chapter 6:	Analysis & Discussion	38
6.1	Water Balance Feasibility	38
6.1.1	Non-Potable Demand vs Rainwater Supply	38
6.1.2	Treated Water Consumption Reduction.....	42
6.1.3	Storage Facility Suitability	43
6.1.4	System Expansion	44
6.2	Economic Feasibility.....	45
6.3	Wider System Benefits.....	46
6.3.1	Stormwater System Reduction	46
6.3.2	Embedded Sustainability Efforts	47

Chapter 7: Conclusions	49
7.1 Conclusions.....	49
7.1.1 Research Question 1: Economic Feasibility.....	49
7.1.2 Research Question 2: Public Perception.....	49
7.2 Recommendations	50
7.3 Future Work.....	52
References.....	54
Appendix A1: Urban Water Optioneering Tool Information.....	i
Appendix A2: Urban Water Optioneering Tool Simulation Model	v
Appendix A3: Rainfall Dataset Backfilling.....	vi
Appendix A4: Occupancy Calculations	vii
Appendix B1: Return on Investment Period Worst Case Scenario	viii
Appendix B2: Return on Investment Period Best Case Scenario.....	ix

List of Figures

Figure 1: Simplified Brabazon Development Plan - Phase 1 Location Highlighted	4
Figure 2: Phase 1 Residency and Planning Diagram.....	4
Figure 3: Methodology Overview	14
Figure 4: Simplified Urban Water Cycle Model.....	15
Figure 5: Weather station reporting period timeline.....	22
Figure 6: Best Case Scenario Feasibility Results	39
Figure 7: Worst Case Scenario Feasibility Results.....	39
Figure 8: Breakdown of the Non-Potable Water Demand and the Collectable Rainwater by Residential Unit Type For the Best Case.....	41
Figure 9: Breakdown of the Non-Potable Water Demand and the Collectable Rainwater by Residential Unit Type For the Worst Case	41
Figure 10: Household Components.....	i
Figure 11: District Network Components	ii
Figure 12: Signal Components	iii
Figure 13: Hydrosystem Components	iv
Figure 14: Urban Water Optioneering Tool Simulation Model	v
Figure 15: Correlation Coefficient Between UOB1 and IBRISTOL29 Weather Stations	vi
Figure 16: Correlation Coefficient Between UOB1 and IBRISTOL3 Weather Stations.....	vi
Figure 17: Return on Investment Period & NPV for Worst case scenario	viii
Figure 18: Return on Investment Period & NPV for Best case scenario.....	ix

List of Tables

Table 1: Estimated Unit Floor Space	23
Table 2: Collectable Roof Surface Area Estimates	24
Table 3: Simulated Roof Collection Surface Areas.....	24
Table 4: Phase 1 Unit Occupancy Assumptions & Breakdown.....	26
Table 5: Summary Information from Phase 1 Occupancy Calculations.....	27
Table 6: Water Consuming Household Appliance Performance Comparison.....	28
Table 7: British Standard Code of Practice Rainwater Storage Tank Sizing Calculation.....	30
Table 8: Best Case Scenario Simulation Results	32
Table 9: Worst Case Scenario Simulation Results.....	32
Table 10: Additional Featured Results from Simulations.....	32
Table 11: Capital Cost Extrapolation (Roebuck, Oltean-Dumbrava & Tait, 2011).....	35
Table 12: Return on Investment Periods for Best and Worst Case Scenarios	37
Table 13: Net Present Value of Total Profit/Loss for the Best and Worst Case Scenarios	37
Table 14: Summary table showing the best case rainwater supply and the worst case non-potable water demand	42
Table 15: Total treated water reduction with the rainwater harvesting system implemented	42
Table 16: Spillwater and system failure summary.....	43
Table 17: Total Number Of Occupants For Each Occupancy Plan.....	vii

Chapter 1: Introduction

This chapter serves as an introduction to this research project into the feasibility of medium-scale rainwater harvesting systems. An important background section discusses the threats that increasing urban populations pose to water distribution networks and the need for making cities and large developments more adaptable to sensitive climates. The sections following the background aim to highlight the role that rainwater harvesting could play in solving these issues, and then introduces the relevance of rainwater harvesting for the chosen case study: The Brabazon Development. Finally, the aims and objectives for the project are defined in conjunction with the research question.

1.1 Background

The current climate crisis is posing a notable threat to the operation of cities around the world, specifically regarding the availability of water. Residents in Cape Town, South Africa, faced a “Day-Zero” scenario in 2017 in which the available water resources were depleted to below 20% of the available storage and a 50l per person per day rationing scheme was on the verge of being enforced (Millington and Scheba, 2020). In Chennai, India, in 2003 and 2004 faced a 12-month shutdown of water distribution networks due to a prolonged drought period whereby water resources were brought in via trucks from surrounding areas (Srinivasan, 2008). These represent two of the most extreme water crises in recent history, but the threat of a water crisis has faced, or is facing, many other major cities like Cairo, Mexico City and Sao Paulo. This uncertainty surrounding water resource availability is paving the way for city-wide “climate-proofing” (Makropoulos et al., 2018). Through improved management strategies and technology, cities are preparing to deal with the varying implications of water scarcity and climate change.

1.1.1 Adapting Water Management Plans

Historically, larger, centralised systems had been implemented to successfully meet the water demand from urban populations. These systems treat and distribute water from a central location and tend to service larger populations. However, the rapidly urbanising populations, varying climatic conditions and resource wastage are limiting the efficacy with which these systems can meet the demand of the serviced population. One means by which city planners and developers are adapting to these challenges is to introduce decentralized water systems which incorporate water saving technologies and more sustainable supply and demand management strategies (Leigh and Lee, 2019). The decentralised system has the advantage of servicing a smaller population, with its own independent water source, allowing it to form part of a more modular and adaptable water management plan (Sharma et al., 2013). While many water sources exist for these systems, rainwater harvesting (henceforth referred to as RWH) has been identified as one promising means of climate adaptation.

1.1.2 The Role of Rainwater Harvesting

The water demand from urban populations can be classified as either potable or non-potable. Potable water demand refers to the water that is required to be at a quality suitable for human consumption. Within a household, this demand originates from taps, showers and baths. On the contrary, the non-potable water demand originates from things such as toilet flushing, irrigation and the use of washing machines and dishwashers. This water can be at a lower quality as the risk to human health from the flushing of toilets, irrigation and washing machines and dishwashers is relatively low. However, the traditional urban water cycle operates in such a way that both the potable and non-potable water demand are met by the supply of water treated to a drinking water quality. The provision of “over-treated” water for non-potable uses shows an inefficiency regarding resource consumption. The role of rainwater harvesting is to

collect and store rainwater to meet the non-potable water demand, thereby reducing the wastage from over-treating water.

1.2 Project Details

This research project explores the use of rainwater harvesting systems from the perspective of a medium-scale residential development called the Brabazon Development. This development represents a suitable case study for this research project as the development aims to open the first phase of residential houses in late 2021 with an overall project duration of beyond 10 years. This early in the project, the outcome of this research then offers the added benefit of acting as an implementable business case for the development.

1.2.1 The Brabazon Development

The Brabazon Development is a mixed-use development located at the Filton Airfield site, just outside the city of Bristol. The intention is to integrate a sustainable residential neighborhood with education and commercial opportunities while promoting the historical significance of the Filton airfield (YTL Developments, 2019). The construction of the development is expected to last for over 10 years, leading to the final phase of homes and office spaces after 2030. However, the first phase of the development, which includes 278 housing units, is currently (as of September 2020) under construction with a scheduled opening in late 2021. This research project focusses on this first phase of the development with the intention that the results and findings from the research providing a useful business case for YTL Developments in the future phases of the development. Figure 1 shows simple plan for the Brabazon Development, with the location of the first phase indicated. Included in Figure 2 is the plan proposal for the first phase of the Brabazon Development which represents the case study for this research. The diagram highlights that the phase includes 1 and 2 bedroom apartments and 2-, 3-, 4- and 5-bedroom housing units (YTL Developments, 2019).

1.2.2 Project Aims & Objectives

There are 2 main aims for this research project which can be defined as follows:

1. To provide an implementable business case for YTL Developments that assesses the economic and environmental suitability of different circular water system options using harvested rainwater as the main source.
2. To build public awareness about the potential for using RWH systems within circular water system solutions.

In order to achieve these main aims, a number of project objectives are used to map out the structure of this research project. These objectives are defined as follows:

1. Analyse the Brabazon Development to identify key components for the simulation models. This includes the different supply (rainfall dataset, estimated collection surface areas and estimated runoff percentages) and demand characteristics (resident occupancy and user water consumption).
2. Using an urban water cycle modelling tool to run simulations to obtain a performance range for the rainwater harvesting system. This will provide an indication of the potential for the system and provides the necessary input water quantities for the economic assessment.
3. Estimate suitable capital, operating and maintenance expenses which can be compared to the potential savings from the substitution of rainwater for treated water to meet the non-potable water demand.
4. Present the water balance scenarios from the water cycle simulations and the results from the economic assessment to determine the feasibility of the system for adoption in the Brabazon Development.

1.2.3 Research Question

The following 2 formal research questions offer guidance on the direction of the project and helps define the successful outcomes of the project:

Question 1: Is it economically feasible to implement a rainwater harvesting system for a medium-scale development?

Question 2: What are the wider benefits of implementing such a rainwater harvesting system, and can these wider benefits improve the adoption of the system by improving public perception?

Chapter 2: Literature Review

In assessing the feasibility of a rainwater harvesting system, a review of existing literature that explores similar case studies and assesses the perception of rainwater harvesting is necessary. Chapter 2 of this report is the literature review which ties together the findings from rainwater harvesting feasibility studies in the United Kingdom and internationally with the intention of identifying key assessment methodology steps. The chapter begins with a description of the scope of the literature review. The sections following the scope definition cover case studies into the economic feasibility rainwater harvesting systems, a review of the public perception to rainwater harvesting and then a summary of the existing literature gap which this research project aims to contribute towards.

This literature review is aimed at identifying a literature gap by considering the existing literature into the feasibility of rainwater harvesting systems from a domestic and a commercial perspective. By analysing existing case studies, it is possible to identify the limitations to the existing literature body and can formulate the literature gap which this research paper can contribute towards.

While the case studies will provide a suitable means of assessing the existing literature body, an assessment of the existing simulation software packages will highlight the most suitable software tool. The limitations of the most suitable tool are then highlighted and means of avoiding these limitations are discussed.

2.1 Rainwater Harvesting Feasibility Case Studies

The feasibility of rainwater harvesting systems is a relatively well researched topic. With the increasing pressure that water scarcity places on city planners and authorities, the use of rainwater as a source

Research into integrated water management systems is well established. Case studies from a variety of developed and developing countries located in areas experiencing varying levels of rainfall are widely available. For the purpose of this literature review, it is only necessary to explore some of the available literature to draw conclusions about the limitations to using RWH and offer some guidance for the selection of the water balance scenarios for the proposed research project.

Research into the feasibility of using RWH as a means of reducing the drinking water demand for the Amsterdam Schipol Airport shows that on a large scale, the use of the RWH systems is not economically viable for potable use (Kuller et al., 2017). The research shows that the harvestable rainwater can adequately meet the demand for non-potable use in the airport and reduces the drinking water demand by 58%, however, the costs associated with the installation of the RWH system are not economically viable over a 30 year return on investment period (the expected lifespan of RWH technology in The Netherlands). In the case of the Amsterdam Schipol Airport, the non-potable water uses are similar to those that can be expected in the Brabazon development as the research included the usage from hotels, hangars and main terminals. The similarities between the non-potable water uses for the airport and the Brabazon development allow the comparison of the systems, however, the airport is expected to service significantly higher numbers of people and the treatment and storage associated with this higher demand will result in an extended pay back period. This research proves that the use of RWH systems on a large scale is not economically feasible, but does offer insight into the method of analysis for the Brabazon development and offers some frame of reference for the scalability of RWH systems. These conclusions highlight that the system economics poses the most notable limitation to the use of RWH technology, as confirmed in literature exploring the public perception of these systems within the United Kingdom (Ward et al., 2013).

Another relatively well researched field is the feasibility of RWH systems for household use. The results of implementing RWH systems often poses promising results for individual

households as the storage requirements are relatively low, and the suitable water uses do not require the use of a treatment process. The limitations to the majority of household research is that the results are not scalable to a mixed-use development such as the Brabazon development. The recent case of this is the city of Tel Aviv, in Israel which shows that the effective implementation of the RWH systems to individual households within the city will reduce the water import needs by 10% (Thi Hoang Duong et al., 2011). Similar improvements in the water savings and drinking water demand can be seen across studies into urban areas across the world (Mwenge Kahinda, Taigbenu and Boroto, 2010; Abdulla, 2019; Ndeketeya and Dundu, 2019). However, this research is limited to domestic uses for RWH. The relatively low exploration of using RWH technology as a water source for a mixed-use development is one literature gap that the proposed research project will contribute to.

The discussed literature shows a number of important considerations and conclusions that are relevant to the Brabazon development. The public perception of the RWH systems show that public adoption of the technology is mostly limited by the cost implications of installation and maintenance. There is research that explores the possibility that economic analyses on the feasibility of RWH systems offer conflicting results (Amos, Rahman and Gathenya, 2016) . The economic feasibility of the RWH systems is highly dependent on the forecasted price of water. This suggestion opens an important consideration for the proposed research project. Nonetheless, the majority of current literature assess the use of harvested rainwater under circumstances that differ from that posed by the Brabazon development. The proposed research will be contributing to this gap by performing a detailed assessment of the most suitable integrated water management solution.

2.2 Simulation Software

A number of urban water cycle simulation software packages exist. The purpose of this research project is to simulate and ultimately set up a water management plan which incorporates a

rainwater harvesting system. For this reason, the software package for this project needs to be able to model the entire urban water cycle by incorporating both the supply and demand characteristics for the modelled area. Research into some of the available urban water cycle modelling software packages highlights their suitability for the management and planning of the rainwater harvesting system (Peña-Guzmán et al., 2017). While other software packages exist, such as Aquacycle, Urban Volume Quantity, WaterBalance and WaterMet2, The Urban Water Optioneering Tool (UWOT) is chosen as the suitable tool for use in this project as it offers the capability of modelling both the supply and demand characteristics of the system within the same model. The limitations to the software are in the GIS capabilities and the economic assessment. For the purpose of this project, it is only necessary to obtain the overall water balance scenarios, for which the UWOT tool satisfactorily achieves. The economic assessment is only notable limitation which can be overcome by performing hand calculations.

2.2.1 Urban Water Optioneering Tool

Rozos, Evangelos and Makropoulos (2013) presented the most recent literature using the UWOT tool to model the full urban water cycle. In this research, the UWOT tool is used to model the water supply and demand model for Athens, Greece. While the Athens model represents a significantly larger system than that of the Brabazon development, the principles behind the building the model remain the same. Stored within the UWOT tools' "technology library" is a variety of household items which have assigned water consumption and frequency of use parameters which correspond to different water-saving options for each item (ie. Shows items have multiple "brands" which offer different water-saving parameters). While the stored database offers a user-friendly operation, the parameters stored within the database may need to be verified and modified according to more up-to-date data. For the UWOT tool to make use of the database information, users are required to input 3 data measurements:

1. A time series of rainfall information that will be used to set up the rainwater harvesting scheme and to aid in the urban runoff from the area using permeability. For this timeseries, it is necessary to have access to primary rainfall data and set up possible forecasts as to the variation the Brabazon development can expect.
2. A timeseries of occupancy demonstrating the population expectations over an extended period of time. This is important information when identifying possible season trends in population expectancy. For the Brabazon development, it is expected that there will not be a significant seasonal variation in population numbers.
3. A timeseries of the number of households. **This information accounts for the influence of urban growth.** For the Brabazon development, the entire project is expected to occur over more than 10 years, with housing areas being completed in stages. This can be seen as a form of urbanisation and thus the rate at which the development expands falls under this timeseries.

Using the information set up in Rozos, Evangelos and Makropoulos (2013) as a framework, the necessary information required for the use in the proposed project is clear. The results from the Athens UWOT model are compared to the operational model used by the Water Company of Athens. The results shown water storage, rainfall and runoff, infiltration and spillage reflect only minor differences. These similarities show that the use of the UWOT tool for the modelling of the Brabazon development offers acceptable simulation results.

The use of the UWOT tool has been integrated into a number of other pieces of literature. In an assessment of water recycling technology, the UWOT tool has been used to prove the benefit of RWH technology by reducing the drinking water demand in households (harvested rainwater can be used for non-potable uses which saves the use of drinking water) (Rozos, E. and Makropoulos, 2012). The effective modelling of these technology alternatives proves that the

UWOT tool is successful in the simulation of integrated water management schemes, hence proving the tools suitability to the Brabazon development.

Chapter 3: Research Methodology

The research methodology defines the work undertaken in achieving the project aims and objectives. This chapter looks at the available means by which the urban water cycle and economic assessments can be completed and highlights the final decisions on the suitable research steps.

3.1 Research Methodology Overview

The feasibility of the rainwater harvesting system requires an understanding of how the system will be able to perform. To do this, a simulation of the complete urban water cycle for the first phase of the Brabazon Development, with an integrated rainwater harvesting system, is required. These simulations are the means for obtaining primary data for input into the economic analysis section of the report. The output of the simulation stage will be the water quantities for the supply and demand characteristics. With the quantified water streams, it is then possible to estimate the potential economic feasibility of the system and draw conclusions about the wider benefits of the system. The general methodology steps used in this research project can be summarised into 3 distinct steps.

1. Urban Water Cycle Simulation: Using modelling software, simulate the urban water cycle with an integrated rainwater harvesting system to determine the quantity of water in the potable water supply network, the harvested rainwater network, the stormwater network and the sewage network.
2. Economic Assessment: Using the water quantities, assess the system's economic feasibility by comparing the cost of the system to the potential savings.
3. Wider Benefit Analysis: using the economic assessment and the water balance scenario, highlight some of potential wider benefits of the system.

A summary of these methodology steps is shown in Figure 3. This figure shows the important factors influencing the supply of rainwater and the demand of both potable and non-potable water. The accuracy of these characteristics is an important factor in determining the feasibility of the rainwater harvesting system.

3.2 Urban Water Cycle Simulations

The urban water cycle simulation is set up in such a way that the harvested rainwater is treated, stored and then distributed to meet the non-potable water demand from the residential units. Where the supply of rainwater fails to meet this non-potable water demand, a “make-up water” stream will initiate and make up the deficit. The make-up water stream is a potable water stream provided by the drinking water distribution network. In the case where the harvested rainwater exceeds the storage capacity, the spillwater stream will leave the system via the stormwater network. This simple urban water cycle is shown in figure 4 and represents a simplified model of the simulated urban water cycle for the first phase of the Brabazon Development.

3.2.1 Simulation Input Data

As introduced in Chapter 1, the Brabazon Development is still in the early stages of the 10-year construction plan. Additionally, there is currently no plan to include a rainwater harvesting system. Given this information, the input supply and demand data characteristics are unknown and need to be estimated. These estimations bring one notable limitation to the research project in that the accuracy of the results can be reasonably questioned. However, by employing an upper and lower limit to the input data for the supply and demand characteristics, a performance range can be obtained which will include the likely performance of the system. This approach also has the added benefit of incorporating a measure of sensitivity to changes in the supply and demand information. To achieve the upper and lower limit for the system's performance, variations in the supply and demand input characteristics are simulated. The lower limit combines the highest demand and lowest rainwater supply characteristics, while the upper limit combines the lowest demand with the highest rainwater supply.

The alternative to the best and worst case methodology is to model a variety of different simulations with different input characteristics. This approach, while it may offer better insight into the effects of different variations, would require significantly more simulations to be run but would not provide any better indication to the feasibility of the system. The reason for this is that even with more simulations, the input information is still estimate-based and the results would still fall in between the best and worst case scenarios. Therefore, the best and worst case scenario offers sufficient information about the feasibility of the system.

Supply Characteristics

The supply characteristics include the daily rainfall, the collection surface area, and the runoff coefficient for the rainfall. The rainfall dataset will be represented by a recorded daily rainfall dataset from weather stations in the Filton area. This approach will include the daily variations in rainfall over a 10-year period. The collection surface areas are represented by an upper and a lower value. The determination of these values starts with an estimate of the collection surface area, and then applying a +15% case to set up the upper limit and a -15% case to set up the lower limit. Finally, research into the effects of roof slope (aspect), construction material and direction in relation to predominant wind direction shows that evaporation (considered the reciprocal of runoff) varies between 38% and 14% (Ragab et al., 2003). The conclusions from this research indicate the importance of promoting runoff, and it is assumed that in installing a rainwater harvesting system, the runoff would not be lower than 70%. Thus, the runoff coefficients will be varied between 70% for the lower limit and 90% for the upper limit.

Demand Characteristics

The water demand from the urban area can be broken down into the potable and non-potable demand. The non-potable water demand originates from the use of toilets, washing machines, dishwashers and irrigation, whereas the potable demand originates from the use of baths, showers and kitchen and bathroom taps. All of these “outlets” have a water rating assigned to them which describes the rate at which each item “consumes” water when in use. The issue

with these ratings is that residents within the zone are not required to meet a specific water rating. Instead, they will install appliances and tap outlets according to their own personal preference to the resulting water bill. As a result, varying the water rating of these items is a suitable means of assessing the potential quantity for both the potable and non-potable water demand. This variation is achieved by simulating 2 categories of water ratings for the different items, a high and a low water consumption category. The details for these different categories are presented in Chapter 4.

In addition to the water consumption rating, the number of people serviced by the system will vary. Due to the fact that the phase is still under construction, there is no data available for the exact number of residents in the first phase homes. Thus, for input into the simulations, different resident occupancy plans are modelled. These variations are based on assumptions about the number of people who can be expected for each different residential unit. The breakdown of the different types of residential unit, so the minimum assumption is based simply off a single person per room. The maximum occupancy is then based on an assumption about the maximum possible resident occupancy for each housing unit. The result will be 4 different occupancies, but only the lowest and highest will be simulated as the best and worst cases respectively.

3.3 Economic Feasibility Assessments

The feasibility of the rainwater harvesting system is largely determined by the economic performance. In a study on the public perception of rainwater harvesting, the majority of people who do not utilise rainwater harvesting systems are concerned by the long return on investment periods and the potential that the system never recovers the initial capital costs (Ward et al., 2013). As a result, a robust economic assessment is required as part of the feasibility assessment for this project.

A return on investment (ROI) period is calculated by comparing the net present value (NPV) of the systems expenses (capital, operating and maintenance) against the potential savings from the system. The economic benefits include the potential savings from substituting treated water with rainwater for the non-potable water demand, the reduction in stormwater network size and the reduced flood mitigation measures. However, for the purpose of this research, only the savings associated with the water substitution is considered. The exclusion of the reduced stormwater system and flood mitigation measures is one limitation to this research. Additionally, these aspects are expected to improve the economic feasibility of the rainwater harvesting system. The lack of information available for these economic benefits is one notable literature gap which should be addressed in order to fully reflect the potential for the rainwater harvesting systems.

Similar to the variation in the supply and demand characteristics, it is important to vary the capital, maintenance and operating expenses as there is little information available for the costs associated with the large scale rainwater harvesting systems.

3.3.1 Capital Expenses

The capital expenses for the system include the purchase/construction of a rainwater harvesting tank and the associated installation costs for the electronic management systems, the system pumps and the pipeline network for the harvested rainwater. In an urban area with no rainwater harvesting, houses will be equipped with a guttering system which collects and diverts water to the stormwater system. Thus, the costs for the guttering system is not an additional expense associated with the rainwater harvesting system. Additionally, internal pipe system within each housing unit remains the same. Thus the only additional costs that a rainwater harvesting system incurs are relating to the purchase and installation/construction of the storage tank, the pumps, the management system, the filter unit, and the necessary

trenching works for the laying of the pipeline network. The details of the estimated capital expenditure for this specific system is covered in Chapter 5.

3.3.2 Operating and Maintenance Expenses

The operating and maintenance expenses associated with the system include the electricity consumption for the operation of pumps and the management unit as well as the necessary cleaning and replacement of items after their usable life is exceeded. Additionally, there is an expected maintenance cost associated with the system which covers the general wear and tear of items. The exact estimation of these costs is outside the scope of this project, but the acceptable assumption that these costs approximate to 5% of the initial capital investment is used for the economic models (Roebuck, Oltean-Dumbrava and Tait, 2011).

3.3.3 Economic Benefit

The economic benefit of the system for this research is limited to the potential water savings from substituting treated water for rainwater. The calculation of the value of water that is saved from this substitution is determined by the price of treated, drinkable water. As a measure of sensitivity, varying future water prices are included in the economic assessments. The 3 variations used are the current water price remaining unchanged, a 1% annual increase and then a 1% annual decrease.

Chapter 4: Urban Water Cycle Simulations

Chapter 3 introduced the research methods associated with the urban water cycle simulations and the economic assessments. This chapter is dedicated to isolating the different input parameters to the Urban Water Optioneering Tool simulations and then presenting the results from those simulations. The chapter begins by considering the different supply and characteristics and then covers the necessary storage information.

4.1 Urban Water Optioneering Tool

The Urban Water Optioneering Tool uses a signal-based approach for the different components of the model. A signal can be viewed as a water stream that either leaves or enters a component. These signals are then used to connect different components within the model to simulate the entire urban water network. There are 4 categories of components that can be used to simulate the water cycle:

1. Household Appliance: This category is used to simulate the components inside the housing units that consume water and then components that represent the distribution networks for water to the houses such as the potable water network and the rainwater network.
2. District Network: This category is associated with the global movement of water from the system including the sewage and stormwater networks.
3. Signal: These components represent changes to the characteristics of different streams and are also used to extract information from the system. Examples of characteristic changes could be a stream diverging into multiple streams or the aggregating of multiple streams into a single stream. The logger components allow users to extract the information from any given stream (signal).

4. Hydrosystem: The hydrosystem components are used to represent the storage, treatment or conveyance of water in the system. Included in this category are components such as the impervious area which is used as the collection surface for the rainwater harvesting system.

These component categories then allow the formulation of the urban water cycle model. Included in Appendix A1 is a description of the different components in the simulation model, and included as Appendix A2 is full representation of the entire simulation model. The input parameters for the different components are covered in sections 4.2, 4.3 and 4.5.

4.2 Supply Characteristics

The supply of rainwater to the system is determined by the expected rainfall experienced in the area, the surface area of the collection surfaces and the water runoff coefficient. By defining these 3 characteristics, the supply of rainwater to the area can be accurately simulated.

4.2.1 Rainfall

The forecasted rainfall in the area is the principal factor in calculating the amount of water the system can harvest. This factor requires the use of a historical rainfall dataset. The University of Bath operates a weather station (now referred to as UOB1) that is located at the Filton site and has a complete hourly rainfall dataset from 16 September 2019 (Kim, 2019). This station represents the most accurate rainfall recordings for the Filton site, but the use of this data is limited due to the short reporting period. By using rainfall datasets from weather stations surrounding the Filton site, it is possible to extend the UOB1 dataset to cover a 10-year period between 16 September 2010 and 1 October 2020. Although the extended dataset will not be an exact representation of the historical Filton rainfall, it will represent an acceptably accurate estimate for this period.

Figure 5 shows a summary of the nearby weather stations and their respective reporting periods. The IBRISTOL25, IBRISTOL137, IBRIST53 and IBRIST73 weather stations are all excluded from this study due to their short reporting period. However, the IBRISTOL3 and IBRISTOL29 stations have acceptable reporting periods for use in this study. Rainfall data is obtained from Weather Underground for each of the IBRISTOL3 (Underground, 2020a) and IBRISTOL29 (Underground, 2020b) stations. To distinguish between these weather stations, Pearson’s correlation (or correlation coefficient) is used to compare the readings from the 2 stations for the period between 16 September 2019 and 25 June 2020 to the readings taken by the UOB1 station. The correlation coefficient that is closest to a value of 1.0 represents a dataset that most accurately replicates the UOB1 station. The results from the correlation coefficient calculation can be found in Appendix A3.

Figure 5: Weather station reporting period timeline

Both weather stations present correlation coefficients above 0.86 which indicates that each of the stations presents a suitable dataset for the use in this project. Eventhough the IBRISTOL3 station shows the lower correlation coefficient (0.86 compared to 0.89 for IBRISTOL29), the IBRISTOL3 station is chosen as the representative dataset for the period September 2010 to September 2019 as this station is the closest weather station to the Filton site.

4.2.2 Collection Surface Area

The first phase of the Brabazon Development has planning approval for 1 and 2 bedroom apartments as well as 2-, 3-, 4- and 5-bedroom houses (Developments, 2019). The exact details of the breakdown of the number of each unit type is not available, but this information does give an indication of the potential roof surface collection area. An estimate for the floor space for each of the unit types is the starting point for the estimate of potential collection surface areas. Table 1 shows a summary of the estimated breakdown of the number of each of the different unit types with an estimate of the floor space for each unit.

Table 1: Estimated Unit Floor Space

Residential Unit Type	Bedroom Breakdown	Assumed Split Quantity	Community Requirements	Estimated Floor Space (m ²)
Apartment	1	68	50	50
	2	68	67	75
Houses	2	36	80	100
	3	36	85	130
	4	35	90	160
	5	35	111	190
		<u>278</u>		

Under the following assumptions, it is possible to translate the floor space estimates into a collectable roof surface estimate:

1. Apartment buildings consist of 34 units per floor (x17 1 bedroom units, and x17 2 bedroom units). Thus, the total collectable surface area is limited to the total surface area of these 34 units.
2. The 2 and 3 bedroom house units are **single-storey**, meaning the total collectable roof surface is the product of the total number of 2 and 3 bedroom units and the estimated floor space.

- The 4 and 5 bedroom units are **double-storey**. For this case, the total collectable roof surface area is defined as the product of the number of 4 and 5 unit bedrooms and half of the total estimated floor space.

Table 2 is a summary of the estimated roof collection surface areas for each unit type. This information represents the initial estimate to which a 15% increase and decrease is applied as a measure of sensitivity. **The best case scenario is represented by the higher collection surface area, and the worst case is represented by the lower collection surface area.** This information is presented in Table 3.

Table 2: Collectable Roof Surface Area Estimates

Residential Unit Type	Bedroom Breakdown	No. of Units with Water Collecting Roofs	Roof Surface Area (m ²)
Apartment	1	17	50
	2	17	75
Houses	2	36	100
	3	36	130
	4	35	80
	5	35	95

Table 3: Simulated Roof Collection Surface Areas

Residential Unit Type	Bedroom Breakdown	-15% Surface Area (m ²)	Roof Surface Area Estimate (m ²)	+15% surface area (m ²)
Apartment	1	867	850	1173
	2	1071	1250	1479
Houses	2	3060	3600	4140
	3	3960	4680	5400
	4	2380	2800	3220
	5	2800	3325	3850
			14138	16700

4.2.3 Rainwater Runoff

Chapter 2 has introduced the influence that roof surface characteristics can have on the collectable water quantity and gave a minimum and maximum interval for the expected runoff in relation to the rainfall experienced. Since information is unavailable on the specific designs of the housing units, assumptions regarding these characteristics are necessary. However, the UWOT tool includes standardised evaporation percentages (the reciprocal of the runoff water quantity). These percentages are 0%, 5%, 10%, 20%, 30% and 50%. The expected runoff percentage is expected to be between 70% and 100%, thereby warranting the modelling of scenarios with 70% and 90% runoff (30% and 10% evaporation cases respectively).

4.3 Demand Characteristics

The demand of potable and non-potable water originates from the number of people being serviced in the urban water system and their respective consumption ratings. These factors play a significant role in the feasibility of the rainwater harvesting system.

4.3.1 Serviced Population

Chapter 3 introduced the assumption-based method for the estimation of the number of resident occupants. The assumption-based method includes 2 resident occupancy plans, a standard and a densified plan. The standard plan represents the 278 units, within which a minimum and a maximum number of residents are modelled. The densified plan intends to highlight the influence that an increased population density has on the feasibility of the system. This plan includes the same number of housing units, but double the number of apartment units. Included in this plan is a minimum and maximum occupancy assumption. Thus, for the input into the Urban Water Optioneering Tool simulations, a total of 4 occupancy plans are presented: a standard minimum, a standard maximum, a densified minimum and a densified

maximum. However, only the minimum and densified maximum cases are modelled for the best and worst case scenarios respectively.

Table 4 shows a summary of the assumptions made regarding the minimum and maximum occupancy totals for each unit type. The total unit occupancy is determined as the product of the number of units in each category and the simplifying assumption. The minimum cases for all unit types is governed by a single occupant per room. The maximum cases differ slightly for each unit based on an underlying assumption relating to suitable family or share house sizes. For input into the Urban Water Optioneering Tool simulations, both the maximum and minimum cases are modelled as an indication of the feasibility for the RWH system for the first phase of the Brabazon Development.

Table 4: Phase 1 Unit Occupancy Assumptions & Breakdown

Residential Unit Type	Bedroom Breakdown	Standard Plan Split Quantity	Densified Plan Split Quantity	Minimum Assumption	Maximum Assumption
Apartment	1	68	136	1 Occupant per bedroom	2 Occupants per bedroom
	2	68	136	1 Occupant per bedroom	2 Occupants per bedroom
Houses	2	36	36	1 Occupant per bedroom	Small Families: 3 Occupants
	3	36	36	1 Occupant per bedroom	Medium Families: 4 Occupants
	4	35	35	1 Occupant per bedroom	Medium/Large Families: 5 Occupants
	5	35	35	1 Occupant per bedroom	Large Families or share houses: 7 Occupants

278

Included in Appendix A4 is a summary of the total number of occupants and the breakdown of each unit occupancy for each modelled simulation. A summary of the totals for the different plans is presented in Table 5.

Table 5: Summary Information from Phase 1 Occupancy Calculations

	Standard Plan		Densified Plan	
	Minimum	Maximum	Minimum	Maximum
Apartment Units	204	408	408	816
Housing Units	495	672	495	672

4.3.2 Water Performance Rating

When considering the performance ratings of the household appliances and outlet taps, it is important to vary the water consumption rating of the different items as this is largely determined by the homeowners preferences. The Urban Water Optioneering Tool offers a range of pre-determined “types” for each water consuming household appliance. These “types” hold different energy and water consumption performance ratings. While each appliance has a different number of pre-set types, the most commonly used are that of the *Conventional* and *Best Available Techniques Not Entailing Excessive Costs* (henceforth referred to as the *BATNEEC* option). The inability to edit these pre-set performance ratings then requires verification of these characteristics. Using the BREEAM (Building Research Establishment Environmental Assessment Method) water consumption rating system as a comparative measure, the pre-set characteristics are verified (Building Research Establishment (BRE), 2011). BREEAM is a commonly adopted assessment method that assigns environmental impact ratings based for determining the environmental impacts of common building components and assigns a rating based on the relative

Table 6 shows the built-in characteristics for the different appliance and outlet tap items in the Urban Water Optioneering Tool and compares them to the BREEAM performance rating parameters. Table 6 shows a simple comparison of the parameter values for the built-in Conventional and BATNEEC features to the Level 1, 3 and 5 BREEAM accreditation

requirements for each appliance. The kitchen sink, hand basin and shower performance ratings for the BREEAM system are expressed in the units of litres per minute. To unify these units, it is assumed that a standard use of the kitchen sink and hand basin is 20 seconds, while the standard shower time is 10 minutes.

The conclusion from this table is that the conventional category roughly approximates to a BREEAM level 3 rating and lower, whereas the BATNEEC category roughly approximates to a BREEAM level 3 rating and above. By modelling both the conventional and the batneec options separately, a measure of sensitivity will be incorporated into the simulation results and also adequately sets an upper and lower limit to the expected water consumption demand for the first phase.

Table 6: Water Consuming Household Appliance Performance Comparison

		UWOT Built-In Features		BREEAM Domestic Use Parameters (Building Research Establishment (BRE), 2011)		
		Conventional	BATNEEC	Level 1	Level 3	Level 5
Potable Water Requirements	Bath (L/use)	130	N/A	180	140	100
	Hand Basin (L/use)	2.1	1.7	3	1.5	1
	Shower (L/use)	60	35	100	60	35
	Kitchen Sink (L/use)	2.1	1.7	3.3	1.7	1.7
Non-Potable Water	Dishwasher (L/cycle)	35	15	13	12	10
	Washing Machine (L/cycle)	60	45	60	40	30
	Toilet (L/flush)	9	4	5	4	3

4.4 Storage Facilities

The storage type and capacity for the system often governs the feasibility of the rainwater harvesting system. Not only does this determine the amount of water the system can expect to collect, but it is also a large contributor to the economic costs for the system. Thus, the optimisation of the storage tank facilities is an important aspect to be considered in any rainwater harvesting feasibility study.

4.4.1 Storage Capacity

For the purpose of this research, an estimated rainwater storage capacity is suitable. The British Standard Code of Practice for Rainwater Harvesting offers insight into an acceptable estimate for the sizing of storage facilities based on 3 methods (British Standards Institute, 2009). The standard method is the most basic calculation which considers the number of residents serviced by the system. The Intermediate method is a more detailed calculation that considers the available rainwater in the area and the number of residents serviced by the population. Finally, there is a detailed calculation procedure which highlights important considerations regarding the variation of rainwater supply and the variation of non-potable water demand. However, there is no calculation procedure as the code suggests the use of specially designed software to estimate the suitable tank sizing. The intermediate approach is considered suitable for this research, with the calculation steps shown in Table 7. The values corresponding to the number of persons (n) and collecting surface area (A) are kept constant as the storage tank sizing is an estimate based on likely supply and demand characteristics. The minimum from the resulting 2 equations is used as a suitable estimate for the sizing of the rainwater tank to which an 20% reduction is applied as this represents the most economically feasible sizing option (Santos and Taveira-Pinto, 2013). The resulting tank size is 430m^3 .

Table 7: British Standard Code of Practice Rainwater Storage Tank Sizing Calculation

Equation	Components	Values
$Y_R = A \times e \times AAR \times h \times 0.05$ Eq. 1	Y_R – 5% of the annual water yield (L)	$Y_R = 542\,958\text{L}$
	A – Collecting Surface Area (m ²)	A = 16700m ²
	e – Yield Coefficient	e = 85%
	AAR – Depth of annual rainfall (mm)	AAR = 850mm
	H – Hydraulic filter efficiency	H = 90%
$D_N = P_d \times n \times 365 \times 0.05$ Eq. 2	D_N – 5% of the annual Non-Potable Water Demand	$D_N = 1\,277\,500\text{L}$
	P_d – Daily requirement per person (L)	$P_d = 70\text{L}$
	n – number of persons	n = 1000

4.4.2 Storage Tank Type

The type of storage plays into the economic assessment of the system. The use of plastic and metal above ground storage tanks presents one feasible option for the storage of water, however there is little economic information available about these tanks at this size. Another option is the underground storage tank, however, the cost information for these storage tanks with the necessary excavation costs are also relatively scarce in literature. The final option is the use of a concrete tank which includes the excavation and laying of foundations, as well as the casting of tank walls. The concrete option is used in this project as there is some available cost information for these systems.

4.4.3 Treatment Requirements

The treatment of stored rainwater is an important aspect of the rainwater harvesting system. Rainwater generally has a low organic and inorganic contaminant concentration and as a result does not require onerous treatment procedures. In general, a filter system is employed to remove larger organic matter such as leaves at a domestic unit level. However, smaller filters may be employed at the storage tanks to remove finer particles.

One of the most common means of treatment is through a total avoidance method of implementing a first flush system (Hofman-Caris et al., 2019). This system allows an initial volume of water to bypass the storage facility and flow directly into the storm network. This initial flow, high in contaminant concentration from deposition and atmospheric accumulation, is then removed, eliminating the need for in depth treatment. This system is employed for the system by removing 1% of collected rainfall (modelled as a filter with a 99% efficiency). However, this system needs to be optimised and should only be employed following a detailed testing of the potential water contaminants on the roof surfaces.

4.5 Simulation Results

The results from the simulations are presented according to the best and worst case scenarios. The important water balance quantities that need to be extracted from the simulations are the potable water demand, the non-potable water demand, the total collectable rainwater, the make-up water, the spillwater, the garden and pavement runoff and the total stormwater. Additionally, an important quantity is the number of failures of the rainwater storage tank. A failure is defined as any day in which the stored rainwater equals a value of zero (ie. When the full non-potable water demand is met by the drinking water network). This number of failures helps to highlight the storage tank sizing issues. Included in Table 8 and 9 are the summary results for the potable and non-potable water demand as well as the collectable rainwater for

the best and worst cases respectively. The remaining quantities for the make-up water, stormwater, runoff from gardens and pavements and spill water are presented in Table 10.

Table 8: Best Case Scenario Simulation Results

	Potable Demand (m ³ /year)	Non-Potable Demand (m ³ /year)	Total Collectable Rainwater (m ³ /year)
Apartments	7007.9	2856.3	1887.9
2 Bed	2473.4	1008.1	2947.1
3 Bed	3710.1	1512.2	3844.1
4 Bed	4809.3	1960.2	2292.2
5 Bed	6011.7	2450.2	2740.7
Totals:	24012.3	9787.0	13711.9

Table 9: Worst Case Scenario Simulation Results

	Potable Demand (m ³ /year)	Non-Potable Demand (m ³ /year)	Total Collectable Rainwater (m ³ /year)
Apartments	35720.8	21641.1	1073.0
2 Bed	4727.8	2864.3	1694.2
3 Bed	6303.7	3819.0	2192.5
4 Bed	7660.7	4641.2	1317.7
5 Bed	10725.0	6497.6	1550.3
Totals:	65138.0	39463.1	7827.8

Table 10: Additional Featured Results from Simulations

	Make-up Water (m ³ /year)	Spillwater (m ³ /year)	Runoff (m ³ /year)	Stormwater (m ³ /year)	Failures
Best Case	1106.1	5000.3	3432.8	8433.1	512.0
Worst Case	31644.7	9.4	3432.8	3442.2	3569.0

Chapter 5: Economic Assessment

Chapter 4 is a presentation of the simulation details and results obtained from the Urban Water Optioneering Tool. Using these results, the economic assessment can be performed. This chapter introduces the details necessary for the calculation of the return on investment period and then presents the results from those calculations. The results from the best and worst case scenario then defines the upper and lower limit to the systems performance range from a net economic perspective.

5.1 Return On Investment Calculation

The calculation of the return on investment period uses the net present value method which compares the cost of implementing, operating and maintaining the system with the potential benefit of the system. Equation 3 is the net present value formula with the necessary component description. This calculation is done from a net cost and benefit perspective. This means the calculation will determine the ROI and NPV for the system considering the net expenses and benefits to society. The analysis section of this report considers these results in the context of the development owner, home owner and authorities.

$$NPV = \sum_{t=1}^n \frac{R_t}{(1+i)^t} \quad \text{Eq. 3}$$

Where:

NPV = Net Present Value

n = Discount Period (years)

t = Reporting period (years)

R_t = Net Cash In- and Outflows (£)

i = Discount rate (%)

The discount rate for the economic assessment is chosen as 30 years. The expected life-span of the storage tank is about 30 years. Since the storage tank makes up a significant portion of the capital expense for the system, after 30 years the system may require an additional capital input. Therefore measuring the feasibility up to 30 years will indicate the potential benefit for the implementation of the system. The discount rate is chosen as 5% as is common in existing literature (Domènech and Saurí, 2011; Roebuck, Oltean-Dumbrava and Tait, 2011).

5.1.1 Capital, Maintenance & Operating Expenses

Medium-scale rainwater harvesting systems are relatively unexplored in literature. One of the most significant limitations to the feasibility of these systems is that there is very little information available about the economic performance of these larger systems. The smaller-scale domestic systems show that the high capital expenses are infrequently recovered by the savings from the system. However, the principle of economies of scale, which suggest that there are improved economic benefits with an increasing scale of output from the system.

Capital costs

The starting point for estimating the capital cost of the system is the small-scale domestic systems. A collection of quotes in the United Kingdom involving the purchasing of an underground tank, a pump, a filter unit, an electronic management unit and the excavation and installation costs for systems ranging between 1.2m³ and 15m³ provide the starting point for the estimation of the system's capital costs (Roebuck, Oltean-Dumbrava and Tait, 2011). The results for these systems are summarised in Table 11. By extrapolating the capital costs for these systems, an estimated capital cost of the 430m³ system for the first phase of the Brabazon Development can be approximated to £72 661.90.

Table 11: Capital Cost Extrapolation (Roebuck, Oltean-Dumbrava & Tait, 2011)

System Size (m ³)	Capital and Installation Costs (£)	Reference/Method of estimation
1.2	2 500	
3	3 200 – 3 400	
4	3 500	
5	3 400 – 4 000	(Roebuck, Oltean-Dumbrava and Tait, 2011)
7	4 000	
11	3 800 – 4 100	
13	4 500	
15	5 500	
430	72 661.9	Linear Extrapolation

As a second means of estimation, this result is compared to a study for a multi-storey building in Spain (Domènech and Saurí, 2011). The results for this research show that a 50m³ concrete tank with the pump, filter unit, and pipelines is estimated to cost approximately €19 000.00 (using 2011 exchange rates approximates to £16 530). Extrapolating this result shows an estimated system price for the 430m³ system to be £142 158.00.

Although these results show significantly different capital costs for the respective systems, for the purpose of this research, they serve as acceptable upper and lower limits to the feasibility of the system at the Brabazon Development. Hence, the Capital costs that are used in the calculation of the economic feasibility of the system is £70 000.00, £100 000.00 and £130 000.00.

Operating & Maintenance

The lack of information available regarding operating and maintenance costs highlight the significance of the literature gap for larger rainwater harvesting systems. However, an operating and maintenance cost of 5% of the initial capital investment is commonly employed

and is used in the economic assessment for the Brabazon Development (Kuller et al., 2017). The nature of the percentage means these operating and maintenance costs will vary with the upper and lower limit to the capital costs.

Although this assumption-based method is less accurate than obtaining actual maintenance cost and completing the full specifications of the system, the purpose of this research is not the full design of the rainwater harvesting system. Thus, the estimated operating and maintenance costs are suitable in determining the feasibility of the system.

5.1.2 System Savings

It has already been discussed that the economic benefit considered in this economic assessment is limited to the savings associated with the substitution of the rainwater for the treated drinking water in meeting the non-potable water demand. As a result, these savings can be estimated by multiplying the volume of rainwater that is “consumed” in the residential units by the future price of treated water.

The price of water is expected to vary over the 30-year assessment period. The nature of this variation is dependent on many factors which may increase or decrease the cost of water. Thus, for the estimation of the potential savings, 3 future prices of water are considered: the current price of water (£1.2669/m³ (Water, 2020)) ; a 1% per annum decreasing water price and then a 1% per annum increasing water price.

The exclusion of the economic savings of the reduced size of the storm water system and the reduced flood mitigation measures do limit the economic feasibility of the system. It is expected that these benefits will improve the feasibility of the system.

5.2 Economic Assessment Results

As explained in Chapter 4, the economic assessment follows a similar sensitivity approach in that the capital, maintenance and operation costs are varied against varying future water prices in the economic benefit. The best and worst case simulation results are applied to

Included as Appendix B1 and B2 are the graphical representations of the return on investment periods. These graphs show the economic performance of each of the best and worst case scenarios. A summary of this information is included as Table 12 and Table 13.

Table 12: Return on Investment Periods for Best and Worst Case Scenarios

		Return on Investment Periods		
		-1% Water Price	Current	+1% Water Price
70k	Worst Case	16 Years	14 Years	12 Years
	Best Case	12 Years	11 Years	10 Years
100k	Worst Case	-	-	27 Years
	Best Case	-	29 Years	21 Years
130k	Worst Case	-	-	-
	Best Case	-	-	-

Table 13: Net Present Value of Total Profit/Loss for the Best and Worst Case Scenarios

		NPV of Total Savings after 30 years (2050)					
		-1% Water Price		Current		+1% Water Price	
70k	Worst Case	£	21,434.67	£	38,223.00	£	58,045.64
	Best Case	£	36,173.21	£	54,665.19	£	76,499.41
100k	Worst Case	-£	31,624.01	-£	14,835.68	£	4,986.97
	Best Case	-£	16,885.46	£	1,606.51	£	23,440.73
130k	Worst Case	-£	84,682.68	-£	67,894.35	-£	48,071.71
	Best Case	-£	69,944.14	-£	51,452.16	-£	29,617.95

Chapter 6: Analysis & Discussion

Chapter 6 is an analysis of the results presented in Chapters 4 and 5. The chapter begins with an analysis of the water balance scenarios to determine the potential for rainwater to meet the non-potable water demand and then explores the opportunities available to improve on these scenarios. The chapter then moves into the analysis of the economic assessment results and discusses the feasibility of the system as well as the possible limitations to the results. Finally, the chapter looks into the wider sustainability impacts and discusses their influence on public perception and adoptability of the system.

6.1 Water Balance Feasibility

The water balance feasibility looks at the ability for the system to meet the non-potable water demand with harvested rainwater and the reduction of treated water consumption through the substitution of harvested rainwater.

6.1.1 Non-Potable Demand vs Rainwater Supply

The rainwater harvesting system shows the potential to be able to entirely meet the non-potable demand under the best case scenario but fails in the worst case scenario. Figure 6 shows a simple summary of the total non-potable demand, spillwater, collected rainwater and available rainwater. These categories highlight the systems' ability to meet the non-potable water demand for the system. The available rainwater for use, which is representative of the spillwater quantity subtracted from the total collected rainwater, sits at approximately 8700m³/year whereas the non-potable water demand sits at approximately 9800m³/year. This shows that the rainwater harvesting system in the best case scenario is only capable of meeting 89% of the non-potable water demand. However, the 5000m³/year spillage stream represents the amount of water that the system "wastes" each year and indicates that the system could be optimized to increase the available rainwater and meet the non-potable water demand.

The worst case scenario shows significantly less feasibility. Figure 7 shows the total non-potable demand, spillwater, collected rainwater and available rainwater for the worst case scenario. The system shows a significant increase in the non-potable water demand, resulting from the significant increase in population size and consumption category. The small spillage stream is a result of the reduced collected rainwater stream and the increased demand which draws water from the storage tank.

As a general indicative range for the performance of the system, these results adequately express the potential for the system. With a dedicated focus on maximising the rainwater supply, the feasibility of the system is still largely determined by the population the system services and their water consumption. The first phase of the development will show a non-potable water demand of between 9800m³/year and 39500m³/year and can expect to collect between 7800m³/year and 13700m³/year. This shows that the variability in the demand from the system outweighs the supply of rainwater and thus it is unlikely the system will be able to meet the non-potable water demand with harvested rainwater.

One important result to highlight is the influence that the density of population has on the feasibility of the system. Figure 8 and 9 show a comparison between the non-potable water demand and the collectable rainwater quantity for both the best and worst case scenarios, broken down into the different residential unit types. For the best case scenario, each of the 2-, 3-, 4- and 5-bedroom housing units have collection surface areas which collect more rainwater than would be required to meet the non-potable water demand. The apartment units are the only residential unit type which does not collect enough rainfall to be able to meet the non-potable water demand. The worst case shows that none of the unit types are able to collect enough water to meet the non-potable water demand. However, considering the best case rainwater collection (which is achievable as this can be integrated into the building designs at a planning stage) and the worst case non-potable water demand, the supplied rainwater would be sufficient in meeting a total of 35% of the non-potable water demand for the zone. Table 14 shows a comparison of the best possible rainwater collection scenario against the worst possible non-potable water demand scenario. The 2- and 3-bedroom units collect enough water to completely meet the non-potable water demand (103% and 101% respectively), with the 4- and 5-bedroom units having the non-potable water demand 49% and 42% met by the supply of rainwater.

Figure 8: Breakdown of the Non-Potable Water Demand and the Collectable Rainwater by Residential Unit Type For the Best Case

Figure 9: Breakdown of the Non-Potable Water Demand and the Collectable Rainwater by Residential Unit Type For the Worst Case

Table 14: Summary table showing the best case rainwater supply and the worst case non-potable water demand

	Apartments	2 Bedroom	3 Bedroom	4 Bedroom	5 Bedroom	
Best Case Supply	1887.9	2947.1	3844.1	2292.2	2740.7	13711.9
Worst Case Non-Potable Demand	21641.1	2864.3	3819.0	4641.2	6497.6	39463.1
	9%	103%	101%	49%	42%	35%

The system's inability to completely meet the non-potable water demand, even under the best case scenario, shows that the economic performance from the system is governed by the amount of rainwater collected. There is added benefit to the reduction of the non-potable water demand from the home-owners perspective, however this is not realised in the improved economic performance of the system.

6.1.2 Treated Water Consumption Reduction

The total reduction in treated water consumption through the substitution of harvested rainwater is represented by the total harvestable rainwater, less the spillwater stream. This quantity is used in the economic assessment for the system. Table 15 shows the total potable water reduction as a result of the rainwater harvesting system for each of the best and worst cases. The best case shows a reduction in treated drinking water by 8711.6m³/year, which is a 89% reduction, whereas the worst case shows a reduction of 7818.4m³/year, which is a 19.8% reduction.

Table 15: Total treated water reduction with the rainwater harvesting system implemented

	Non-Potable Demand (m ³ /year)	Harvested Rainwater (m ³ /year)	Spillwater (m ³ /year)	Treated Water Reduction (m ³ /year)	% Treated Water Reduction
Best Case	9787.0	13711.9	5000.3	8711.6	89.0%
Worst Case	39463.1	7827.8	9.4	7818.4	19.8%

6.1.3 Storage Facility Suitability

The system feasibility is largely determined by the suitability of the storage facilities. For this system, an estimated 430m³ tank was used as the storage facilities with a starting volume of 0m³. Table 16 offers some indication of the suitability of the storage tank. In the best case scenario, which is set up to maximise the amount of collectable rainwater, the spillwater quantity of 5000m³/year shows that the tank is significantly too small. Considering the total collectable rainwater each year approximates to 13 700 m³, the system loses 36.4% of the collectable rainwater. The 512 system failures (meaning 512 days out of the 3864 day simulation period – 13.3%) confirms that the smaller demand quantity from the residential units results in a lower quantity of water removal. For the worst case scenario, the system shows a significant reduction in spill water, but a significant increase in system failures. The large increase in water demand from the residential area draws more water from the system. To compound the infeasibility of this scenario, the reduced rainwater collection surface area and the reduced runoff percentage results in less water being supplied to the storage tank. The 3569 system failures is a clear indication of the infeasibility of this case by highlighting the influence that home-owner consumption has on the system feasibility.

Table 16: Spillwater and system failure summary

	Spillwater	Failures
Best Case	5000.3	512
Worst Case	9.4	3569

The large spillwater quantity in the best case scenario suggests an increase in the storage tank volume will improve the system feasibility. However, the most notable determinant of the system feasibility can be tracked back to the demand from the residential unit. In order to

optimise the system, collaboration between home-owners to limit the water consumption ratings is vital in promoting the system feasibility.

6.1.4 System Expansion

This research paper focussed on the first phase of the Brabazon Development, but the results can be extrapolated across the rest of the development area. The system has been set up to represent 278 units. However, the Brabazon Development aims to provide approximately 2800 homes with additional commercial and office space. The resident density of the apartment units represents the most infeasible residential unit, so there is a need to include additional collection surface areas to account for these apartment units.

One of the options would be to make use of the Brabazon Hangar as a collection surface. The hangar is intended as an entertainment arena, meaning the potable and non-potable water demand will be insignificant during periods where the arena is not in use with spike decreases when the arena is in use. However, this 26 acre (105 000m²) (Wilson, 2019) hangar area offers a promising option for rainwater collection. This surface area is approximately 6 times larger than the simulated collection surface area and will provide a significant water quantity for addition to the system.

Other options include using the commercial and office buildings as collection surfaces. While these structures will also hold their own non-potable water demand, the system can be expanded to include these structures. Their performance and the feasibility of using these structures needs to be explored as part of a future research project, but the larger rainwater harvesting system may lead to a more economically feasible system.

One additional benefit of expanding the system across the development is the potential for a reduced capital cost for the purchasing and operation of the storage tanks. The expansion of the rainwater harvesting system is undoubtedly a significant project. YTL Developments can use this as an advantage in supporting local rainwater harvesting system providers and the

commitment to such a large system may result in lower capital costs for the system – improving its economic benefit.

6.2 Economic Feasibility

Under specific circumstances, the system can be economically feasible. However, the feasibility results presented in Chapter 5 take on a global perspective which does not consider the costs and benefits to the homeowner and development owner (in this case, YTL Developments). By separating the system economics into the homeowner and development owner perspectives, the system is unlikely to be implemented.

As expected, the feasibility of the rainwater harvesting system is highly dependent on the initial capital investment. Without a robust economic model that incorporates current commercial prices for the installation of the storage tank, pumps and the pipeline network, the economic assessment is significantly limited. However, the results from this economic assessment are aimed at providing an estimated range for the feasibility of the system. Using the best and worst case scenario water balance results and a range of potential capital, maintenance and operating costs, the economic potential for the system is adequately expressed.

The feasibility for this system also shows a dependency on the amount of rainwater collected. The demand of non-potable water is likely to exceed the available rainwater due to the fact that the non-potable demand quantity varies between 9787m³/year and 39400m³/year, whereas the harvestable rainwater varies between 7800m³/year and 13700m³/year. Thus, for the system economic benefit to be maximised, emphasis needs to be placed on maximising the possible collectable rainfall. By maximising the rainfall collection, the system is able to achieve the economic performance as expressed for the best case scenario (potential savings after 30 years ranges between £1 600 and £76 000). However, this is under the strict condition that the capital expenses remain lower than £100 000. The system shows absolutely no economic feasibility if the capital expenses exceed this threshold.

Additionally, the future price of water holds a key role in the economic feasibility. An increasing water price improves the potential savings that the system provides. With the threats of climate change and water scarcity in urban areas, the price of water will vary. The system actually benefits from an increase in water price which proves that the implementation of the rainwater harvesting into urban water management plans is an effective means of climate-proofing.

However, these economic feasibility results are expressed from a global, more holistic perspective. In reality, there are separate stakeholders that incur the cost from each the capital, maintenance and operations as well as a separate stakeholder benefitting from the savings from the substitution of rainwater for treated water. From the perspective of YTL Developments, their primary objective for the Brabazon Development is to make a profit on the sale of the residential units and the commercial office space. It is unlikely that YTL Developments will sell the residential and office space and then continue to maintain and cover the operating expenses for the rainwater harvesting system, especially considering that the economic benefit from the reduced water bill is to the advantage of the homeowner. Therefore, the system is unlikely to be implemented.

6.3 Wider System Benefits

The system offers benefits that extend beyond the ability to meet non-potable water demand with harvested rainwater and the economic performance. The wider system benefits may hold less significance when it comes to the public adoption of rainwater harvesting, but these wider benefits may also highlight important characteristics of the system which should be explored and presented as part of the marketing strategy.

6.3.1 Stormwater System Reduction

The rainwater harvesting system has the added benefit of reducing the amount of stormwater needed to be handled. The storage of the collected rainwater is able to achieve a reduction of 8700m³/year in the best case scenario and 7800m³/year in the worst case. Had the rainwater

storage system not been implemented, the stormwater network would have been required to deal with between 11200m³/year and 17100m³/year, depending on the characteristics of the roof surfaces (roof characteristics influence the runoff of water as discussed in Chapter 4). The reduced stormwater network size will cost less in its construction and installation. Additionally, the reduced stormwater quantity and the availability of water storage means an improved flood mitigation strategy can be implemented. The economic benefit of a smaller stormwater system and the reduced damage potential from floods adds to the economic benefit of the system. However, it is difficult to value these benefits without rigorous testing and a robust economic pricing model for the construction and installation of water pipeline networks.

6.3.2 Embedded Sustainability Efforts

The treatment of water to a drinkable water quality requires the input of energy and material. Disinfection often makes use of chemical additives or the use of energy intense operations such as ultraviolet treatment or fine mesh filtration. Additionally, the distribution of this treated water from a single, centrally located treatment facility requires pumping and the use of large, outdated infrastructure.

By implementing a rainwater harvesting system, the first added benefit is that the water distribution distance is significantly lower than if treated potable water were provided to the system. This reduces the power requirements for the distribution of water to contribute towards meeting the non-potable water demand.

The use of “overtreated” water also means the environmental impacts from the treatment of water to a drinking water quality are avoided. By using appropriately treated water for the non-potable water demand, the system has an improved resource efficiency and reduces waste.

One final additional benefit is that the storage of rainwater offers a measure of “climate-proofing” the urban area. As introduced in Chapter 1, many urban cities are faced with the implications of water scarcity. By collecting and storing rainwater, the development affords

itself some degree of water security. The resilience to the expected water price increase resulting from water scarcity is also one means by which the development advocates for its internal sustainability agenda.

Although the wider benefits of the system are explored from a qualitative perspective in this project, the quantitative approach to these benefits would provide an additional boost to the public perception of the system and improves the widespread adoption of the technology.

Chapter 7: Conclusions

Chapter 6 is the conclusions and recommendations of the research. In this chapter, conclusions about the feasibility of the system are made and discussed in relation to the limitations of this research and within the context of the research questions presented in Chapter 1. Additionally, the economic feasibility and wider sustainability benefits are combined to identify possible recommendations for the implementation of a medium-scale rainwater harvesting system, specifically in relation to the Brabazon Development.

7.1 Conclusions

The rainwater system poses a suitable alternative water source to meet the non-potable water demand for a medium-scale urban development. This research highlights the importance of designing buildings with a rainwater harvesting system in mind. By promoting the runoff of water from the collection surfaces, the system feasibility is significantly improved.

7.1.1 Research Question 1: Economic Feasibility

From a holistic, global perspective, the system has been proven to be feasible, even under the worst case scenario, provided the capital costs are between £70 000 and £100 000. However, as the different costs and benefits are broken down by the relative influence on different stakeholders, the system becomes infeasible. From the perspective of YTL Developments, the system should not be implemented. However, there are means by which the system can be implemented successfully that is economically beneficial to YTL Developments. These options are covered in the recommendations section 7.2.

7.1.2 Research Question 2: Public Perception

As explored in (Ward et al., 2013), the common limitation to the implementation of rainwater harvesting is the inability to recover capital costs and a relative misunderstanding of the

potential benefits of the system. This research highlights the potential for a medium-scale system and shows that larger systems are able to recover the capital costs and show a net economic benefit. However, the long return on investment periods remain a significant limitation to the adoption of these types of systems.

The results from the simulations highlight the wider benefits of a rainwater harvesting system. The system offers a measure of security against an increasing water price and offers some resilience to water scarcity. Additionally, the improved resource consumption efficiency promotes a sustainable agenda which may improve the demand for residential units in the Brabazon Development. Future work into these wider benefits may result in an improved adoption of these systems.

7.2 Recommendations

The feasibility of the rainwater harvesting system is limited by the fact that development owners, in this case YTL Developments, incur the entirety of the capital expenses without benefitting from the reduced operating expenses. Additionally, the maintenance expenses incurred are then required to be covered by the development owners. However, developers typically build these types of developments and then sell the units to return a profit on the sale prices of the real estate. Therefore, there is no responsibility for the maintenance expenses when considering a rainwater harvesting system that is planned on a neighborhood scale. For the system to be beneficial to all stakeholders, the following recommendations offer suitable options for the systems implementation:

1. The system could be installed and operated by Wessex Water, a subsidiary of YTL Developments. The capital and maintenance expenses would be covered by Wessex Water. In order for them to benefit from this, they would then need to charge homeowners for the non-potable water consumption. The options for this charge would be at the current price of water, or at a slightly reduced rate. The benefit to homeowners

is that their water bill will, in the worst case scenario, be at the same charge as if there was no rainwater system installed. However the wider benefits of the rainwater system would still be achieved with the profit from this system would then fall to Wessex Water and YTL Developments.

2. A dedicated rainwater harvesting company could be employed to install, operate and maintain the system over its usable life span. This company (potentially owned by YTL Developments) would front the capital, operating and maintenance expenses of the system and then charge the homeowners a rate that matches the current water price each year. This option will realise the full economic benefit from the system as profit to the operating company.
3. YTL Developments could also look to realising the capital expenses from the system in the sale prices of the residential units. Although the increase in price will be minimal, it is then possible to recover the capital expenses from the system. Homeowners then benefit from a reduced monthly water expense, while covering the operating and maintenance expenses in a rates bill to the development. This option requires an exploration of the potential rate prices and requires a guarantee that the system can meet the non-potable water demand from harvested rainwater.

The net system feasibility highlights the need for detailed planning around its installation and operation. There is an economic benefit to adopting this system as part of the network for water supply, but it needs to be feasible for the stakeholder responsible for covering the capital expenses from the system. The 3 options presented offer some means of ensuring the system benefits all stakeholders in such a way that the system is adoptable. The wider benefits from the system will improve the economic performance, but prior to the quantification of these benefits, the savings from the system need to be directed towards the capital investment stakeholders.

7.3 Future Work

This research highlights the net benefit of the rainwater harvesting system based on a number of estimates and assumptions. Although effort has been put into ensuring these estimates are as accurate as possible, it is important to refine these estimates according to more up-to-date and accurate information. From the perspective of building on this research project, the following future research areas are identified as being of significant benefit to the existing literature body.

1. Optimisation of the Brabazon Development system: By optimising the storage tank size and location, the volume of the first flush system and the characteristics of the surface collection areas, the systems feasibility can be greatly improved. Additionally, the research would offer a more detailed estimation of the potential for the system. The research found in this project offers a guideline, or framework, for the assessment of the system and can be adjusted to include more detailed supply and demand characteristics.
2. Current market assessment on the economic details from the rainwater harvesting system: The current lack of pricing information for large scale developments is one significant literature gap regarding rainwater harvesting. By exploring the capital, operating and maintenance costs, specifically for the Brabazon Development, would contribute useful economic indicators for the improvement of rainwater harvesting systems.
3. Rainwater harvesting system's suitability for government subsidies: Exploring the wider benefits of using rainwater harvesting shows that there is an embedded sustainability benefit which may be of interest to government authorities. By quantifying the wider benefits of the system, governments may look at subsidising the capital investment for the systems, thus improving their adoptability.

4. Economic assessment of the benefits from a reduced stormwater network and flood mitigation strategies: Currently, only the savings from the reduction of potable water consumption is explored as the economic benefit for the rainwater harvesting systems. By quantifying the economic benefit for the reduction in stormwater pipelines and the reduced flood mitigation measures, the system will show a significant improvement in its economic feasibility.
5. Expansion of the Brabazon Development rainwater harvesting system: This research paper only explored the use of the rainwater harvesting system for the first phase of the Brabazon Development. While this represents a medium-scale rainwater harvesting system, there is an opportunity to explore the feasibility of the system on a larger scale for adoption across the Brabazon Development. With the development still in its planning stages, proving the system feasibility may result in its early adoption as a means of climate-proofing the area. The adoption of the technology may also increase the demand for the housing units and office space.

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Appendix A1: Urban Water Optioneering Tool Information

This appendix presents a simple description of the components used in the Urban Water Optioneering Tool simulations and are adapted from the built in software component descriptions (Watershare, 2015).

Household Components

Figure 10 shows the common household components simulated in the Urban Water Optioneering Tool. These components operate in the same way, they emit 2 signals. The first is a demand signal, shown at the bottom of each component with a “(-)”. This signal represents the amount of water each component requires per use and according to the frequency of use as defined by the user – essentially defining the water supply to the component. The second signal

is the resulting water emission, shown as either a greywater or a blackwater stream. This signal represents the 'consumed' water – defining the amount of water that needs treatment after the component use.

District Network

The district network components represent the pipeline networks for the sewage, potable water, stormwater and the greywater lines. Figure 11 shows the 4 district network components. They are similar in that they all receive and emit 1 signal. The input and output signals represent the water in each system, however the component includes a leakage factor which reduces a small portion of the water as waste.

Signal Components

Signal components represent changes to the different streams regarding water volumes. A summary of the relevant signal components is shown in Figure 12.

The standard and inline logger components are used to extract the stream information from the simulation model. These components are put in place to record the quantities and quality of water streams so that the data can be exported from the software.

The Mix component is used to join multiple streams with the resulting single stream taking on the quality of the lowest quality stream. The Sum component is used only for the summation of streams in which the quantity of water in the stream is necessary.

The Multiply component is used to represent the number of similar units. In creating the household units, an occupancy is defined to specify how many people will be using the component. However, in cases where there are multiple residential units, the multiply component is used to replicate the household components to replicate the entire urban area.

Hydrosystem Components

The hydrosystem components are used to convey, treat and store water in the urban water cycle. The relevant hydrosystem components are shown in Figure 13.

The pervious area is used to simulate the garden, or green spaces. This component allows some water to pass through to the water table. The rainfall dataset that is imported is simulated with a defined percentage being removed from the system as infiltration. The Impervious area is the

opposite. This component uses the imported rainfall dataset to quantify the surface runoff. The only losses from this component are determined by the defined evaporation percentage. This component is used to represent the pavement areas for the stormwater runoff stream and then for the rainwater harvesting collection surface area.

The Tank component simulates the storage facility for the rainwater harvesting system. There are 4 signals for this components. The input signals are the water in and water yield. The water in stream represents the water stream from the collected rainfall. The water yield stream represents the non-potable water demand from the residential units. The output signals are the water from system and the spill streams. The water from system is the make-up water stream which results from the storage tanke being empty and not being able to meet the non-potable water demand. The spill tank is the stream that results when the storage tank is full and there is additional water being passed into the tank.

Appendix A2: Urban Water Optioneering Tool Simulation Model

Figure 14: Urban Water Optioneering Tool Simulation Model

Appendix A3: Rainfall Dataset Backfilling

Figure 15: Correlation Coefficient Between UOB1 and IBRISTOL29 Weather Stations

Figure 16: Correlation Coefficient Between UOB1 and IBRISTOL3 Weather Stations

Appendix A4: Occupancy Calculations

Table 17: Total Number Of Occupants For Each Occupancy Plan

					Original Plan			Densified Plan		
Category	Unit Type	Bedrooms	Max. Assumption	Min. Assumption	Unit Quantity	Max. Occupancy	Min. Occupancy	Unit Quantity	Max. Occupancy	Min. Occupancy
Cat. 1	Apartment	1	2	1	68	136	68	136	272	136
Cat. 2	Apartment	2	4	2	68	272	136	136	544	272
Cat. 3	House	2	3	2	36	108	72	36	108	72
Cat. 4	House	3	4	3	36	144	108	36	144	108
Cat. 5	House	4	5	4	35	175	140	35	175	140
Cat. 6	House	5	7	5	35	245	175	35	245	175
Occupancy TOTALS:					278	1080	699	414	1488	903

Appendix B1: Return on Investment Period Worst Case Scenario

Figure 17: Return on Investment Period & NPV for Worst case scenario

Appendix B2: Return on Investment Period Best Case Scenario

